

Study of the pseudo-first order reaction kinetic of Fe(III) complex of N-Salicylidene-L-alanine with catechol in aqueous micellar medium as a model of catechol dioxygenase[†]

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Abstract : The [Fe(sal-L-ala)]Cl.H₂O complex, which is derived from salicylaldehyde and L-alanine amino acid has been well characterized. In this work the reaction of this complex with phenolate substrate catechol in aqueous surfactant medium has studied. The oxygenation reaction has found to be pseudo-first order and rate constant values are calculated using spectrophotometric techniques. Enzyme kinetics of the oxygenation reaction has also been thoroughly examined. The work has proposed as model of catechol dioxygenase.

Keywords : N-Salicylidene-L-alanine, catechol, surfactant, oxygenation reaction, enzyme kinetics.

Introduction

The oxidative cleavage of catechol and other dihydroxy aromatic compounds is a key step in the biodegradation by soil bacteria¹. The catechol dioxygenases are a class of non heme iron enzymes that catalyze the oxidative cleavage of catechol. On the basis of regioselectivity, dioxygenases are classified into two ways, (a) intradiol dioxygenases, which utilize non-heme Fe^{III} centre by surface activation mechanism and (b) extradiol dioxygenase generally using non-heme Fe^{II} centre via oxygenation activation mechanism¹⁻³.

Fig. 1. Enzyme catalyzed reactions of intradiol dioxygenases.

Many attempts to model the catechol dioxygenases have been reported. In these cases the ligand which are used to prepare complexes with metal center always resemble the active site of intradiol dioxygenase. The peroxy adduct decomposes by a Criegee-type rearrangement to muconic anhydride¹⁻⁷.

In this work the reaction kinetics of the oxygenation

reaction of catechol using [Fe(sal-L-ala)]Cl.H₂O in aqueous micellar medium has reported. The biomembrane environment has provided by the aqueous micellar medium. CTAB, SDS and Triton X-100 are used as cationic, anionic and neutral surfactant medium respectively. N-Salicylidene-L-alanine ligand is used in the analysis as it can mimic the active site of the catechol dioxygenase enzyme.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

L-Alanine was purchased from Merck chemicals. The synthetic procedure of the Fe^{III} complex of N-salicylidene-L-alanine [Fe(sal-L-ala)]Cl was previously reported³.

We used cationic micelle CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide), anionic micelle SDS (sodium dodecylsulphate) and neutral micelles Triton X-100 in our experiments and all micelles were purchased from Sigma Chemicals Co., USA and used without further purifications. Tetramethylammonium bromide (TMAB) were obtained from Spectrochem. Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. The TMAB was used as counter ion in micelles. UV-Visible spectra were recorded in a Hitachi U-3210 model as well as in Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 UV/Vis spectrometer. The

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

oxygenation kinetics experiments were performed in a 10 mm path length Thunberg quartz cuvette. pH dependent measurements were made by Adair Dupp. and Co. (India) Model number DPH-77 pH meter. The pH electrode was SCE glass combined electrode which was standardized with known buffer solution. Throughout the work 2%, 4% and 3% (w/v) solution of SDS, CTAB and Triton X-100 are used. These concentrations are adjusted above the level of critical micellar concentration (cmc).

Results and discussion

The present work is done in aqueous micellar medium such that it can provide a bio membrane environment to the reaction center. The concentrations of the aqueous micellar medium are adjusted well above their critical micellar concentration. It favours the complete micellization of the complex and also reduces the chance of any change in absorbance value due to any minor fluctuation in the micelle concentration. Depending on the nature of the surfactants medium the electronic spectrum of $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})]^+$ complex has exhibited variation of their band positions as pH of the solution is maintained.

The interaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})]^+$ with catechol is carried out at high pH level (i.e. $\text{pH} > \text{pK}_a$). On addition of 1 equivalent of catechol (1 mM) to an aqueous surfactant solution of ferric complex (1 mM) at high pH value ($\text{pH} 10.5\text{--}10$), new bands in the range 490–510 nm and 380–395 nm are observed. Comparing these spectral positions with the spectra of related phenolate complexes of iron^{3,8-10}, the band around 490–510 nm (ϵ , $300\text{--}350 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is assigned to phenolate $\rho_\pi \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(d_\pi^*)$ LMCT transition and band around 380–395 nm (ϵ , $710 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is assigned to ligand based band. The colour of the solution changed from light violet to red. The band at 510 nm in the visible region is an indication of binding of cat^{2-} to iron in $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})]^+$ complex ion.

The investigation of the oxygenation reaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})(\text{cat})]^-$ adduct, which is produced *in situ* (with the help of base), had been done in aqueous surfactant medium. The reaction is analyzed by monitoring the slow change of the absorbance of the phenolate(π) \rightarrow iron(III)($d\pi^*$) LMCT band (λ_{max} 510 nm). Gradual decrease of absorbance, at band position 510 nm (λ_{max}), with time indicates the decomposition of the substrate¹¹⁻¹⁵. The reactivity of the oxygenation reaction in aqueous

surfactant medium can be exemplified by comparing the change of absorbance (λ_{max} 510 nm) both in presence or absence of O_2 .

The oxygenation reaction is carried out in all the three micellar mediums using the following procedure. $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ of $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})]^+$ was encapsulated in aqueous cationic surfactant micelle (CTAB). The pH of the solution is increased to 11.0 and equivalent molar amount of substrate (i.e. cat^{2-}) is made to react with complex. The interaction of substrate with Fe^{3+} complex is evident from the change of colour of solution to violet. The solution of substrate- Fe^{3+} complex adduct is exposed to O_2 (air) at room temperature. The oxygenation kinetics was measured by monitoring the slow disappearance of the lower energy charge transfer band at λ_{max} 510 nm as shown in the Fig. 2. The process is considered as pseudo-first order kinetics due to an excess of dioxygen^{6,12}. The electronic spectrum of the reaction mixture after 36 h show the disappearance of the 510 nm band indicating the completion of the oxygenation reaction. The rate constant (k_{obs}) was calculated by fitting the decrease in intensity of the band into the following equation applicable for relatively slow reaction

$$A = A_\alpha + (A_0 - A_\alpha) \exp(-k_{\text{obs}} t)$$

where t is the time, A , A_0 and A_α are the absorbance at the time t , 0 and α respectively, and k_{obs} is the pseudo-first order rate constant (Fig. 3). The second order rate constant is then calculated from the equation^{14,16-18}.

$$K_{\text{O}_2} = \frac{K_{\text{Obs}}}{[\text{O}_2]}$$

Fig. 2. Progress of the reaction of $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})(\text{cat})]^-$ (generated *in situ*) encapsulated in CTAB micelle with air at 27 °C monitored by UV-Visible spectroscopy. The spectra are shown at 1 min intervals.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log(A - A_\infty)$ vs time observed at 436 nm of $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})(\text{cat})]^-$ (generated *in situ*) with O_2 at 27 °C in CTAB micelle.

The oxygenation reaction is also studied in anionic (SDS) and neutral aqueous micellar solution (Triton X-100) (Table 1). The rate of the oxygenation reaction indicates that rate of the reaction depends on the nature of the surfactants and Lewis acidity of the ferric complex. For $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-}$

Table 1. Kinetic data for the oxidative cleavage of $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})(\text{cat})]^-$ in different aqueous surfactant micelles at 27 °C temperature (analyzed after 36 h)

Solvent	k_{obs} (10^{-5} s^{-1})	K_{O_2} ($10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
CTAB	11.5 ± 0.2	9.7 ± 0.1
SDS	16.3 ± 0.1	14.6 ± 0.2
Triton X-100	7.6 ± 0.1	6.2 ± 0.2

ala)(cat)]⁻ adduct rate of the oxygenation reaction in surfactant micelles decreases in the order SDS > CTAB > Triton X-100. SDS is an anionic surfactant with negative hydrophilic head group and dodecyl hydrophobic tail group with Na^+ as the counter ion. In anionic surfactant, negatively charged complex part (i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})(\text{cat})]^-$) undergo slight repulsive interaction which may also influence the Lewis acidity of the metal center. High values of k_{obs} in SDS micelles is a manifestation of this interaction and it implies that the complex acquire some sort of advantage with respect to oxidation because of this micellization. In support of the above argument, redox measurement can also strengthen the idea. The $E_{1/2}$ values of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ redox potentials of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})(\text{cat})]^-$ in the three different micellar medium are measured. A more negative value of $E_{1/2}$ of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ couple is observed in SDS micelle. This may be attributed to the stabilization of the Fe^{III} centre by coordinated phenolate ligand; the surfactant environment may also con-

tribute to this. The incorporation of coordinated phenolate depresses the $E_{1/2}$ of the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ couple of the parent complex by 40–150 mV and this reflects the decrease in Lewis acidity of the iron center on substrate binding. This supports the involvements of Fe centre in the dioxygenation reaction^{11,12,16}.

Several investigations have demonstrated that the reactivity of the model system is influenced by the Lewis acidity of the iron centre. A high Lewis acidity usually caused a high reactivity and that is one reason for the large number of model compounds containing pure nitrogen donor ligands and the low number of complexes containing electron donating phenolate donors to mimic the tyrosine groups of the enzyme^{3,19}. The present coordinatively unsaturated iron(III) complex has bound to phenolate substrate without replacing the already bound phenolate or any other of the primary ligands. On binding of the phenolate (i.e. cat^{2-}), two new phenolate $\rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ LMCT bands appear in the visible region, which is strikingly similar to that observed for the enzyme-substrate complexes in steady state conditions. So, the phenolate adducts containing only one bound donor are suggested as good synthetic model for an enzyme-substrate complex in which the equatorial but not the axial phenolate is bound to Fe^{III} ^{1-4,12,20,21}.

The activity of the ferric complex can be exemplified with *in situ* prepared complexes. The reactivity and position of the M \rightarrow L CT band is influenced by the amount of base added to the reaction mixture of catechol and ferric complex. The addition of base assists deprotonation of the substrate. Highly favourable reaction condition is provided by the addition of approximately 1 to 2 equivalent bases and consequently UV-Visible bands are shifted to a minimum energy. Saturation kinetics is done by plotting initial rates (V_0) vs concentration of catechol ($[\text{S}]$). According to best known model of enzyme kinetics (Michaelis-Menten kinetics) K_m (Michaelis constant), V_{max} (maximum rate achieved by the system) and k_{cat} (turn over number) are calculated by applying Lineweaver-Burk or Eadie-Hofstee plots (Table 2). From the initial velocity measurements

Table 2. Steady state kinetic parameters for $[\text{Fe}(\text{sal-L-ala})]^+$ with substrate cat^{2-} in different aqueous micellar medium

Medium	K_m (μM)	k_{cat} (s^{-1})	k_{cat}/K_m ($\text{M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
CTAB	87	48.1×10^{-1}	6.5×10^4
SDS	94	40.2×10^{-1}	4.1×10^4
Triton X-100	92	46.9×10^{-1}	5.5×10^4

(V_0) the values of K_m and V_{max} can be obtained in several ways, like, substrate saturation curve, Double reciprocal plot and Eadie-Hofstee plot. K_m , V_{max} and k_{cat}/K_m values obtained from these different experimental plots are in well agreement with each other. These values strongly suggest that the complex of $[Fe(L)]^+$, the “active site” of the model reaction, is formed before combining with the substrate. The constant k_{cat}/K_m indicate the efficiency of the concern enzyme. These values encourage the utility of the proposed enzyme^{1,16}.

Conclusion

The ring cleavage of dihydroxy aromatics by ferric complex in aqueous medium has been studied^{19,20}. Lewis acidity pH of the medium and concentration of substrate, affect the rate of the oxygenation reaction. The kinetics of the cleavage reaction is also supported by the study of the enzyme kinetics of the process. These overall results have helped in the projection of the concern system as a model of dioxygenase enzyme.

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